

APPROACHES TO LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: The teacher must make sure that students understand the specifics of the subject, realize that the main thing in learning a foreign language is to be able to understand the acquired material when listening, reading a text, be able to use it in their own statements, and this is achieved only by practice, daily repetition. Multimedia programs have unlimited possibilities, which makes it possible to present any type of activity in the form of animation or image. In foreign language lessons, training presentations, all kinds of information objects: lexical, grammatical material, texts, dictionaries are most often used.

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There are various approaches to teaching English, the main thing is to choose methods that are suitable for you and your students. Each teacher chooses his own method of teaching English. The emergence of new information technologies related to the development of computer facilities and telecommunication networks made it possible to create a qualitatively new educational information environment as the basis for the development and improvement of the education system. The use of information technology opens up new opportunities in teaching a foreign language, because modern training programs, the use of the Internet have advantages over traditional teaching methods, activate the potential of knowledge, skills, and communicative competencies of a student. Students have the opportunity to participate in contests, contests, quizzes, testing conducted on the Internet, take part in video conferences, receive information on a problem of interest, news, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc. One of the most effective ways to use a computer is to use multimedia presentations. The teacher uses an interactive whiteboard in the lesson, attracting the attention of the entire group of students. Multimedia programs have unlimited possibilities, which makes it possible to present any type of activity in the form of animation or image. In foreign language lessons, training presentations, all kinds of information objects: lexical, grammatical material, texts, dictionaries are most often used. The most affordable way to use information technology in a foreign language lesson is to use cognitive and educational programs. Programs are most often compiled in a playful way, which allows students to easily and quickly learn new material, consolidate previously learned. Learn English Euro talk Interactive thematic illustrated vocabulary has great potential in vocabulary learning. This program allows you to train vocabulary on nine different topics. Among the exercises, special attention is paid to practically necessary forms: the perception of foreign speech by ear, speaking and the development of memory. The effectiveness of the application of information and communication technologies in the field of teaching a foreign language depends on the chosen methodology, methods and forms of their application. It is very important how competently the teacher owns the methodology of working with computer technologies, which resources

are used in pedagogical activity. The communicative method: To create a communicative atmosphere in the lesson, it is important to maintain the high activity of each student. Even if the children are silent, they can be busy with mental work: think about their answer, comprehend the statements of the interlocutors. It's not easy to create such an environment. It is important for the teacher to collect the attention of all those present with the task of extracting and using information from the dialogue or the monologue of students, and commenting on the response of their comrades. It is very important to encourage the answers of each student for perseverance, ingenuity, originality of thinking. Project method: One of the ways to activate students in the process of teaching foreign languages is the project method. A training project is a complex of search, research, graphic and other types of work performed by students on their own with the aim of a practical or theoretical solution to a problem. Types of projects that students can use: - role-playing games, stage plays (holidays, music programs, performances, etc.); - research (regional studies, generalization of scientific knowledge, historical, etc.); - multimedia presentations, educational projects; - creative (essays, translation, quizzes, crosswords, etc.); Creative tasks motivate students, create the foundation for cooperation, communication of all participants in the educational process. In order to maintain the interest of students in a foreign language during its study, methodological techniques are used that activate the speech-cognitive activity of students. Each lesson is communication in a foreign language, knowledge of the life of the country and the people of the languages studied. The necessary didactic material, additional literature contributes to the formation of skills and abilities of all types of speech activity (all kinds of supports, test tasks in grammar, vocabulary, reading; texts for listening, educational games). Integrated lessons in Uzbek and English are interestingly held. By demonstrating interesting aspects of life and culture of the native land that are characteristic only for a given nation, attention is also paid to the formation of a steady interest and love for one's village, city, and one's homeland. Students listen to information about the Republic of Uzbekistan, about its capital, about the architectural heritage and sights of the city of Tashkent, about Uzbek cuisine. Schoolchildren especially like the work of compiling and solving crossword puzzles on country studies topics, designing exhibitions, stands, drawings, and essays. Non-traditional forms of lessons have a positive impact on the relationship between teacher and student, create an atmosphere of cooperation and creativity, contribute to the achievement of common goals. The system of teaching the English language is built in accordance with the general didactic principles of upbringing education, science, consciousness, accessibility and feasibility, taking into account the individual characteristics of students.

In the strategy of developing education, senior pupils require special attention, the educational activity of which is required in connection with a change in the content of various academic disciplines and the need to prepare older students for further self-education. One of the important didactic principles is the principle of stimulating a positive attitude of students to learning, the formation of cognitive interests, and knowledge needs.

Depending on the concept of language education of the school as a whole, as well as on the number of hours devoted to learning a foreign language, the contingent of students, a change of emphasis occurs for the purpose of learning. Mastering the English language is associated with the formation of the student's pronunciation, lexical, grammatical, spelling skills, on the basis of which the ability to understand listening, speaking, reading and writing develops and improves. Accordingly, the methods and technologies of language teaching are selected.

Not a single subject of the school course requires such a constant, systematic work of students as a foreign language. The teacher must make sure that students understand the specifics of the subject, realize that the main thing in learning a foreign language is to be able to understand the acquired material when listening, reading a text, be able to use it in their own statements, and this is achieved only by practice, daily repetition.

Skills are developed only during the systematic implementation of certain actions with educational material, such actions that allow you to repeatedly listen, pronounce, read and write in the target language.

The older the students, the greater the importance of the ability to use teaching aids: reading texts, a dictionary, a grammar reference; ability to listen and understand various audio and video texts. So, closer to the older stage, more emphasis is placed not on the amount of knowledge gained, not on remembering rules and tables of conjugations, but on developing the skills of students' independent activity: the ability to independently find the necessary information using the same dictionaries and reference books. Each teacher selects those methods and techniques of work that are most suitable in each case. Long-term practice shows that many students, even in high school, are not able to fully use the information that is contained in school bilingual dictionaries, most of which are used to translate foreign words into Russian and vice versa. The methodology most often also offers job options for teaching students the ability to use dictionaries to quickly find words.

Teaching high school students how to work independently will expand their meanings and provide an opportunity to achieve practical, educational and educational goals in learning a foreign language. Of great importance is the question of organizing the systematic work of students in a foreign language. Desire, the ability to work, the joy of the work performed constitute the basis of successful learning.

The listed learning situations, in my opinion, are an effective means of organizing the active independent work of high school students. The inclusion of students in a situation of choice and evaluation allows students to gradually form the correct assessment of their capabilities. The students' positive attitude towards learning in general depends on the correct choice, planning and evaluation of their abilities. Creating pedagogical situations of communication in the lesson allows each student to show initiative, independence, and ingenuity in the ways of working. The atmosphere is created for the student's natural expression.

CONCLUSION

This research has found several strategies promoted by the lecturer when teaching speaking to young learners. In the classroom activities, the lecturer used several strategies such as, role play, watching videos, jazz chant, digital storytelling, games, and repetition. The teachers might face several barriers in the classroom such as reluctant students, missing pronunciation and lack of vocabularies.

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